

●●○ Public
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PROGRAM GUIDEBOOK

2022

Grassroots Public
Health Design Sprint

PHP PATHFINDER PROGRAMS

Public Health Human-Centred Design Sprint

9 Session Online Program

For: A-Level or Higher Education Students

Benefit/Outcome: Skill development & social project support

Grassroots Public Health Design Sprint

6 Session In-Person Program

For: Community Members

Benefit/Outcome: Skill developments & social impact concept project

Human-Centred Design for Organisational Public Health

1 or 2 Full or Half Day In-Person Sessions

For: Organisations or Companies

Benefit/Outcome: Skill development & concept pitch

PROGRAM SUMMARY

This Pathfinders guidebook offers you a roadmap and reference to open pathways to make society healthier.

Public Health is integral to the quality of life in our communities. It covers mental, physical, social, and environmental health. Public health means health starts in Bristol's community, at home, at school, and in our environment.

It is vital that people have the power to make a difference, and we believe that communities understand what's required to make their society healthier. So, we developed a Human-Centred Design Pathfinders training programme.

Human-Centred Design (HCD) is the approach, and design thinking is the mindset that enables people to explore challenges and design solutions. We use a double diamond method which includes four stages:

1. Discover the challenge (week 1)
2. Define the problem (week 2)
3. Develop the project (week 3)
4. Deliver the solution (week 4)

This programme empowers young people to use their knowledge of real-world challenges to develop practical solutions to make their communities healthier.

In 2020 we asked 500 18-25 year-olds about COVID-19 and public health. 71% of respondents felt their voices were not being heard. 75% highlighted the need for more public health education. So we developed Pathfinders training to empower young people to determine their futures. In 2021 we piloted the training, and 100% of the participants agreed the training was helpful.

Our goal is to train young people using HCD to support them with designing a project in response to the design challenge. Thus, the outcomes for the participants are three-fold:

- Improve individual health
- Develop practical and soft skills
- Empower young people

What is global is local and what is local is global. We look forward to empowering Pathfinders in Bristol to help build our vision of a world in which all generations can discover, create and shape healthier futures.

“

The Pathfinders Program provides a platform for us to determine the future

Zoë, 23, in Essex

WHAT TO EXPECT..

This course is intended to harness and develop skills we already have. Things such as empathy, critical thinking, and communication are naturally occurring skills that develop in many different forms, perhaps in ways you didn't even realise. The goal of design thinking here is to show you how these skills can be used.

Your team will use your collective insights and knowledge alongside HCD research methods to focus on the design challenge we have presented to you regarding your community. Using your personal experiences and investigating those of other community members, your team will be able to determine the real problem and develop a possible solution.

You will work together in teams throughout the HCD stages based on the double diamond framework. Before the program begins we will quickly survey your role and activity interests to form the most balanced teams. In your teams we will provide guidance (not rules) for general role categories so that the program experience is as balanced and inclusive as possible.

In this Pathfinder Program there is a low level of out-of-session work required, however some small tasks might need completing outside of the sessions.

The outcome of this program will be project concept, presented through a simple pitch presentation and the completion of one of the project models provided. This guidebook also provides space throughout the stages for notes or process documentation and for feedback. It is best used printed but digital copies will also be provided and is meant to be kept for future reference.

“

The structure of the design workshops was great at helping to narrow focus on an overwhelming topic.

Rebecca, 22, in Winchester

THE DESIGN CHALLENGE

Investigate why young community members may have low confidence in health providers and experts. Develop a project to help a local charity work alongside your community to improve young people's relationships with health providers and experts.

TIPS FOR GOOD TEAMWORK

Roles

The facilitators will guide roles and group work-sharing. Team roles are an opportunity to gain experience as an information manager, project coordinator or researcher.

Roles can be agreed upon and easily changed throughout the program. We encourage an inclusive approach where the team members can share work responsibilities and gain experience in roles that interest them.

Organisation

Roles can help plan work, especially out-of-session. We encourage sharing workloads, and communication in case a members cannot complete on time - they can update with their team and facilitators to organise cover.

Documentation as you go

Make sure you select at least one team member (changing each session) to take notes throughout the session to have a reference point to look back on. Taking these notes will help later to connect the dots and problem-solving.

It's also good practice for members to take personal notes for developing thoughts or ideas.

SUPPORT & RESOURCES

Facilitators are available throughout the program for your support. On top of facilitating the sessions, they are happy to explain or clarify anything, offer guidance, and give feedback when desired.

Group members are welcome to join a Bristol Pathfinders WhatsApp group where they can discuss, raise questions, and channel feedback.

INTRODUCTION

OVERVIEW

Design thinking is at the core of the Grassroots PHP Pathfinders Program.

We aim to offer community youth members tools that empower them to explore innovative paths to address public health issues in their community.

Design thinking is the underlying design mindset with which we apply human-centred design.

INTRODUCTION TO HUMAN CENTRED DESIGN

Human-Centred Design (HCD) is a design approach to problem-solving that puts the people most affected directly at the centre of the process.

Designers use empathy to understand the people's perspectives and identify real needs and the real problems behind them.

HCD helps those creating solutions break down false assumptions and surface-level problems or 'symptoms' of the real issues. This ensures the solutions developed are effective, impactful and accepted by those directly affected.

The approach is a guideline for designers to help adapt to different contexts and needs. For this program, we will base our process on the HCD Double Diamond Framework, which covers four stages that follow one another, Discover (week 1), Define (week 2), Develop (week 3), and Deliver (week 4).

This approach is handy for such grassroots projects as public health issues are complex and multi-faceted, making it difficult for outside organisations to understand the challenges in the community, which can lead to ineffective solutions and interventions. Facilitating community members as designers empowers those with lived experience to use their knowledge to design solutions their communities want.

THE PROCESS

In the Discover stage, groups use their collective knowledge to explore the context of the core problems drawn from the design challenge. Then the team will develop a research method to validate their assumptions and further understand the context.

At the Define stage, the groups will extract the insights from the previous step and narrow their focus by identifying themes and opportunities for change. Thus, enabling them to define the real problem your team will address.

This is an iterative process, where the teams break down the design challenge and build it with a human-centred understanding of the problem.

Once the Discovery and Define stages are complete, the groups move on to develop their solutions.

At the Develop stage, they explore possible solutions to address the defined problem. Using the team's values, they will determine the best solution for which they want to create a prototype.

In the final stage, Deliver, the teams consider which pathway would be best to implement their solution, i.e. a social project or social entrepreneurship. Last, the groups will explore methods of communication and storytelling to get your solutions out into the world.

DESIGN THINKING AS A MINDSET

Design thinking is the foundation of HCD and can be viewed as both a mindset and a process. As a mindset design thinking is the way one looks at and solves problems. Design thinkers take a step back and look at the big picture, then when the context is better understood, they focus in on what they wish to solve. The benefit of this is that prevents them from looking past important factors that aren't so obvious at first and might have an unexpected influence.

Another key aspect of design thinking is empathising and looking at problems through multiple perspectives. This helps create the best possible solutions, rather than ones made through one viewpoint, which can often be based on assumptions and false beliefs, leading to ineffective solutions.

Design thinking is a problem solving and critical thinking mindset that allows you to uncover obvious and hidden human needs and creatively develop solutions. As a process, design thinking can be confusing and seem messy in the early stages. But trust the process. Clarity will come. The lack of direction in the research stage is actually important to finding the right problem and developing the best solution.

DISCOVER STAGE I

EXPLORE

OVERVIEW

In the discover stage I, we will take a step back and explore the core problems of the design challenge.

The aim is to better understand the context of the design challenge by dissecting as many factors, causes, and consequences as we can consider.

Next, we will look at all stakeholders involved or affected by the problem. Understanding the who and the what will help develop research directions and focus points. These insights will come from personal insights and assumptions we hold.

The next stage will be to validate our findings through research.

SKILLS

Empathy

Communication

Critical Thinking

Organisation Skills

SESSION OVERVIEW

The teams will be determined. No roles should be considered in this session. As with all sessions, everyone will be brainstorming.

This session aims to dissect the problem by asking questions and considering the factors that make up the problem.

After which, we consider the stakeholders; who are involved, influenced, and impacted.

OBJECTIVE

Discuss and understand the context of the design challenge.

KEY TERMS

Brainstorming

A group discussion method for generating ideas and thoughts

Stakeholders

Groups of people or individuals that affect or are affected by something

Systems Thinking

A way of thinking that takes all factors of a context into account and how they influence each-other

SESSION EXERCISE 1

Brainstorming Mind Map

In teams, use the template provided to discuss and document your collective understanding of the context around the design challenge as a team. Begin with the core problem in the middle. Then discuss the influencing factors and note them as topics or themes. After, consider their respective causes and consequences.

SEEP

Consider the Social, Economic, Environmental, and Political factors that make up the problem.

Systems Thinking

Most things are connected in some way or another. Consider the connection in your context.

Share

This stage is about open discussion and discovery! Your ideas or thoughts do not need to be complete or developed to share with your team.

Engage

Questions and discussion will often lead to further insights and ideas otherwise not uncovered. Ask questions about each other's thoughts and ideas.

SESSION EXERCISE 2

Stakeholder Map

Now that your team has explored the 'what' and the 'how', let's discuss the 'who'. The template provided shows 3 categories for stakeholders. Consider which individuals, groups, communities, entities, organisations, or institutions are involved and where they fit on the stakeholder map based on their influence or how they are affected by the problem.

Factors

Use your mind map as a reference when discussing how stakeholders are involved.

Influence

Some stakeholders might influence factors of the problem more than others, in positive and or negative ways. What does this say about their involvement?

Affected

Some stakeholders might be affected, others may have no influence, and some might be both affected and have influence. Consider these connections.

DISCOVER STAGE II

RESEARCH

OVERVIEW

In the discover stage ii, we will take our initial insights from the previous stage and consider the best research method to help validate and further understand our problem.

Teams must consider if qualitative or quantitative research would support their research more or if a balance might help.

Qualitative research will give you answers to 'why?' and quantitative research will often more easily give you answers to 'what?'.

In the next stage, we can use this additional research to identify insights that will help more clearly define the problem on which teams want to focus.

SKILLS

Research Skills

Critical Thinking

Problem Solving

Listening & Observation

SESSION OVERVIEW

Opportunities for team role categories will be explained. Teams can then consider whether they wish to split the roles or share the roles. Remember, roles are not set in stone, and teams are welcome to change roles in a later session.

Teams will develop three additional research methods themselves to use as a toolkit. The teams will develop the research methods throughout the session, which they will then complete out-of-session through engaging with other community members.

OBJECTIVE

Develop a further research plan to gather community insights.

KEY TERMS

Qualitative Research

Research that focus on understanding concepts, opinions, or experiences

Insights

Gaining a new understanding of someone or something

SESSION EXERCISE

PART 1

Interview Stakeholders

Consider the factors discussed in the previous session during the mind map exercise and which stakeholders they apply to. Develop a few questions that your team can ask these community stakeholders in order to gain further insights. The goal here is to have each team member ask someone at least one question and bring the results back to the next session.

Experience Insights

For genuine experience insights, it is helpful to ask behavioural questions rather than opinion-based questions. For example, 'Could you describe a time when you last..?' might provide the best insights.

Perception Insights

If your team wants to gain insights into public perception of a topic, questions like; 'What do you think about..?' are helpful.

Who

Ask any stakeholder, whether it be a family member, friend, random pedestrian, employee somewhere, and so on. However, make sure the stakeholder matches your question context to get the best insights.

What do you think about... ?

How do you feel about... ?

Could you describe a time when you.. ?

Have you ever experienced.. ?

Could you define.. ?

SESSION EXERCISE

PART 2

Personal Experiences

For this research method, we will tap into and reflect on past experiences you have had. As a team, develop a few questions you can ask yourselves to reflect on how you might have experienced a factor, cause or consequence identified during the mind-mapping exercise.

The goal here is to reflect and answer one of these questions (no more than a small paragraph) and bring the results to the next session.

Experience

Consider what happened, how, and who was involved. Try to reflect this objectively.

Feelings

Reflect on how factors and instances made you feel, whether before, during, or after.

And
then..

I
was..

..which
made
me feel..

I
thought..

SESSION EXERCISE

PART 3

Active Observation

For this last research method, we will create mini-challenges to observe some of the factors discussed in the previous session.

Observation can often provide more insights than we think, especially when combined with the other two research methods. Develop a few observation challenges to document an aspect of the problem.

Each team member should document a challenge by writing a description, photographing it, or recording it.

Dissect The Scene

Try to consider what is happening and why. Who is involved, and what role do they play?

Observe
how...

Observe
someone
when..

Observe an
interaction
of..

Observe
a place..

DAY 1 FEEDBACK & REFLECTION

Do you feel inspired about the challenge you are addressing?

Do you feel like you really empathised with the challenges that your audience faces in this process?

Did you identify assumptions or possible biases?

What do you think are some of your biggest unknowns?

DEFINE STAGE I

INSIGHTS

OVERVIEW

Define i is all about processing and analysing the research so far.

We will pick out individual insights from research that we can categorise by topics. Once complete, we can further analyse these individual insights by grouping them into themes and opportunities.

This will help us de-clutter our research and find options for narrowing our focus.

In the next stage, we can use these options to understand better who we will be helping with our project and how we might help them.

SKILLS

- Communication
- Collaborative Thinking
- Critical Analysis
- Organisation Skills

SESSION OVERVIEW

In this session, we will extract insights from our gathered research and turn each individual insight into an individual sticky note for affinity mapping. By doing this, we can isolate the insights for easier organisation.

Then we will group these insight sticky notes together as themes and opportunities for improvements or change.

OBJECTIVE

Identify research insights and potential opportunities to solve problems.

KEY TERMS

De-Clutter

Remove unnecessary messiness and organise things into more digestible ways

Pain Points

Problems or difficulties that your target audience experience in the context of your problem

SESSION EXERCISE 1

Affinity Mapping

In pairs, go over the research gathered from your out-of-session research methods and extract individual insights, which you can note on sticky notes. Then we split the research up evenly so that pairs do not overlap.

While doing this, organise these individual insights into categories of topics (see example).

Each insight on a sticky note should make sense on its own and without the supporting questions or context.

Individual Insights

These should be as simplified as possible. Think of individual insights as an important stand-alone piece of information in the context of the problem.

Topics

Organising the insights in groups under topics will help organise the process, prevent confusion, and provide oversight.

Getting stuck

When in doubt if something is an insight or not, note it down anyway. If it isn't important, this will become apparent in the next step, so no problem.

SESSION EXERCISE 2

Grouping Insights

In this exercise, we remove the topic categories and place the insights bunched together. Then your team will go over the cards together, breaking them up and grouping them together under themes and opportunities for improvement or change.

By doing so we can create new connections and develop our understanding of where improvements or changes might make sense.

Themes

This might be as simple as a recurring problem or an important factor influencing the problem.

Pain points

Recurring themes will often arise in the form of problems or challenges the target audience faces. Thus, addressing such themes makes the opportunities for improvement or change clearer.

Opportunities

Do not hesitate to note down your thoughts on defining the opportunity (in a different sticky note colour) and add it to the grouping!

DEFINE STAGE II

FOCUS

OVERVIEW

In define ii, we will narrow our focus on who we will design for, then define the problem we will address.

First, we will develop personas of our target audience to help understand what kind of pain points they have and what they might gain from a solution.

By understanding our target audience, we can use insights and opportunities to develop our 'how might we' statement, which will clearly define what problem we will address.

This process will allow the team's focused direction to be developed into a solution more readily in the next stage.

SKILLS

Creativity

Empathy

Feedback Skills

Problem Solving

SESSION OVERVIEW

Each participant (or in pairs) will create a user persona of their ideal image of the target audience using a template provided.

After this, we will define the problem your team will address based on our new understanding of the context. We will provide a template to help break down how to describe the problem effectively.

Then we can develop a 'How might we' challenge statement which aims to clarify which problem we will solve, for who, and to what end.

OBJECTIVE

Refine your design challenge by deciding on the problem your team is best suited to address and ideate potential solutions

KEY TERMS

User Persona

A characteristic description of an example of your target audience

Target Audience

A generalised or specific group of people you are trying to solve a problem for

Challenge Statement

A way to describe the problem to help clarify how you can solve it

SESSION EXERCISE 1

User Personas

In pairs, use the templates provided to come up with your ideal target audience personas. Think of this as a perfect example of someone you will design your solution for the design challenge for.

Remember that when you design for a particular set of people, your design can often neglect others that don't fit into the description and have other needs.

Personas are part of building an inclusive design and should be considered ideal users and not absolutes. In other words, they provide a spectrum of the audience to consider.

Personal Knowledge

Since this is a grassroots project, feel free to incorporate characteristics or entire personas of people you know fit the context. This might even give your project that extra genuine edge.

SESSION EXERCISE 2

'HMW' Mapping

This exercise will build on the previous session where your team identified themes and opportunities. Use the sentence template provided to create rapid 'how might we' statements based on the identified themes and opportunities.

After your given time is up, discuss as a team and place these statements on the map template accordingly. Based on the placement of these statements and your team's values, discuss and decide on the best statement with which to move forward.

How might we [create a solution] for [what to solve and for who] so that [desired outcome]?

Specifics

Remember, this statement can be as broad or specific as required since developing your solution comes later. Try not to let the specifics stump you.

How might we...

How might we...

How might we...

DAY 2 FEEDBACK & REFLECTION

What are some of the key insights or connections your team identified in this design stage?

How and why have you defined the problem you're looking to address?

Turn your 'How might we..' statement into a 'How would you..' question and ask someone in your community.

DEVELOP STAGE I

IDEATE

OVERVIEW

In the develop i stage, we will come up with solutions for our 'how might we' statement and map them against feasibility and relevance.

Then based on the outcome of the mapping, we can determine the most logical / best fit solution for the team.

Once the solution direction is decided, we can then develop the concept further with a user journey map that helps us understand the different stages and audience interactions that will occur during the implementation of the solution.

Once we understand what our solution might look like from beginning to end, we can develop a prototype visualisation in the next stage.

SKILLS

Creativity

Analytical Thinking

Problem Solving

Planning & Organisation

SESSION OVERVIEW

Here we will ideate the solution pathway using a priority map. This allows us to consider the feasibility and relevance of an idea as we brainstorm them together.

We can evaluate which solution sits in your team's ideal spot on the priority map by ideating with this priority map. Now we can decide on a solution and consider how the user journey will look.

By creating a user journey map, we can fill in the holes of the solution concept, considering user touchpoints, interactions, and other factors from start to finish of the implementation.

OBJECTIVE

Brainstorm possible solutions for the project and then work to develop how your solution might look using a journey map.

KEY TERMS

Ideate

Create ideas for a specific purpose such as problem solving

Priority Map

An axis of values that allow you to place key information on for comparison and analysis

Feasibility

The degree of ability to achieve a certain outcome or goal

User Touchpoints

A point of contact or interaction between the user and the solution

SESSION EXERCISE 1

Ideate Solutions

Collaboratively work to generate possible solutions for a 'how might we' statement. Using the 'crazy 8' method, develop rapid solutions. Then share and discuss where to place them on the provided priority map (feasibility/impact axis) template. This should help put into perspective how realistic or suitable an ideated solution might be. Have each team vote on a solution with which to go forward.

Ideas

No idea is too small or insignificant! On the contrary, noting down small or even silly ideas can help boost your creativity and help you come up with even better ideas later on. Creativity is a muscle we can improve with practice! So try not to block yourself with judgement, let the ideas flow freely,

SESSION EXERCISE 2

Journey mapping

Once your desired solution is decided on, your team can take a fitting user persona you have developed and map out what this solution would look like from beginning to end. The user journey template presents implementation stages and experience categories from the user's perspective for each stage.

Scenario-Based Design

Consider the journey map to be one possible reality of your solution, so try not to have contradicting facts or statements.

Journey Steps Which step of the experience are you describing?	Discovery	Initial Experience	Overall Experience	Sharing
Actions What does the user do? What information do they look for? What is their context?				
Needs and Pains What does the user want to achieve or avoid?				
Touchpoints What (and how) do they interact with?				
Customer Feeling What is the customer feeling?				
Behind the scenes				
Opportunities What value are we creating?				
Process ownership Who leads this interaction?				

DEVELOP STAGE II

CREATE

OVERVIEW

In develop stage ii we will develop our solution further by creating a prototype visualisation.

This will not include all of the stages and detail your team created in the user journey map. Rather, it will be one stage of the solution implementation. This might be as the target audience interacts with the solution or a part of the solution itself, or maybe when they become aware of it, or perhaps after they encounter it.

The idea is to have fun visualising the solution concept your team came up with. Ensure the teams document this visualisation in some form or another so that you can use it in the next stages!

SKILLS

Creative Empathy

Communication

Collaborative Teamwork

Feedback Skills

SESSION OVERVIEW

In this session, we will develop a simple prototype visualisation of the solution concept. This might be in the acted physical form or designed physical form. It should only be a visualisation of the solution, like a snapshot - rather than the finished solution.

OBJECTIVE

Work to develop and complete the project prototype, get feedback, and refine the prototype to achieve the project outcome.

KEY TERMS

Visualisation

Creating a visual representation of an idea, situation, or object

Prototype

A basic version of something for presentation and feedback

User Experience Scenario

A situation that a user might experience while interacting with an implemented solution

SESSION OPTION 1

Storyboarding

Teams can use the template provided or use a preferred format for this option.

Come up with a scenario your target audience might go through while interacting with your project outcome.

As a team, visually communicate what is happening and why. Have one or more of the team members contribute to the drawing of the storyboard, and the rest contribute to the descriptive text.

Remember!

The ideas of what to draw and why are much more important than the quality of the drawings themselves.

Storyboard of Story Title Description	Key Goals and Objectives Key Tasks and Deliverables	Context Key Activities and Tasks			
Trigger	Incident	Starting Step	Continuing Step	End State	
Who	Who	Who	Who	Who	Who
What	What	What	What	What	What
When	When	When	When	When	When

SESSION OPTION 2

Role Playing / Skit

This option is a fun way to act out a scenario your target audience might go through while interacting with your project outcome. As a team, consider how to best act out a situation that can communicate the ideas and aspects of the solution you are conveying. It could be just 2 members of each team showing an interaction or everyone depicting a scene.

Humanise

This option is a great way to humanise your solution. Take up the role of the personas you have created and behave you feel they would.

Humour

Making things funny is a great way to leave a lasting impression on your audience!

<p>Story Title</p> <p>Introduction</p>	<p>Key Facts and Points</p> <p>Key Facts and Examples</p>	<p>Conclusion</p> <p>Key Benefits and Value</p>
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Topic	Summary	Primary Step	Secondary Step	Conclusion
<p>Why</p> <p>What</p> <p>How</p>				

DAY 3 FEEDBACK & REFLECTION

1. What are three obstacles your persona might encounter along their journey?

2. Why are do you feel project will help a local charity work alongside your community to improve young people's relationships with health providers and experts.

3. b) Which stakeholder are you going to present your solution to - and - why are you going to present to them?

3. b) What do you think this stakeholder will say about your solution?

DELIVER STAGE I

LAUNCH

OVERVIEW

Deliver stage ii will help consider what it might look like if we were to launch this solution concept and implement it in the real world.

Teams will decide which pathway is best for them to design a solution; social entrepreneurship or a social project. Each path has a model template to help the teams understand what factors will be needed to achieve implementation.

After this, we will look at how a simple pitch presentation structure can help convey the message and effectively present your concept to interested parties like partners or investors.

In the following stage, the teams will work to complete this pitch presentation.

SKILLS

Analytical Thinking

Problem Solving

Collaborative Learning

Planning & Organisation

SESSION OVERVIEW

This session aims to develop a conceptual launch strategy based on one of the two models provided; the Theory of Change or the Business Canvas Model.

Then, we will start to develop storytelling skills and dissect what a simple pitch structure might look like.

OBJECTIVE

Complete the project by understanding the theory of change and how to launch the project. Then bring this all together with storytelling in a concise, simple presentation pitch deck.

KEY TERMS

Launch Strategy

A plan or action-plan for turning a project into a reality

Theory of Change

A method for planning, participation, management, and evaluation of a project

Pitch

A term used for a quick and concise way of presenting

SESSION EXERCISE

Theory of Change

"If you can't explain it simply, you don't understand it well enough" - Albert Einstein.

What is the Goal?

A vision statement is a clear statement of your objective. Here are a few examples: Alzheimer's Association: A world without Alzheimer's disease. Feed the Children: Create a world where no child goes to bed hungry. Honda, in 1970: We will destroy Yamaha.

The important detail we gain from these vision statements is it outlines the project's ambition. If your project looks to build and improve relationships between communities and health providers, what is the goal of your project?

Agree on how to define this goal in teams.

You don't need a vision statement yet, but thinking about this will help you develop a Theory of Change (TOC).

TOC is an excellent tool for all charities, not-for-profit organisations, and even businesses, and it is a great way to develop a roadmap and communicate a strategy!

When building a TOC, we work backwards [from the goal back]. It is counter-intuitive. But helpful. Generally, we start with a clear goal and develop from there in reverse gear from your Goal, Outcomes, Outputs, Activities, and Resources [e.g., your team is a crucial resource!].

In this session, we will build a theory of change so that each team has a clear path to delivering the change they want to see in the world!

DELIVER STAGE II

PITCH

OVERVIEW

The final stage, deliver ii!

Today, the teams will present their pitch and give and gather feedback.

In addition to getting external feedback, this is an opportunity to celebrate the completion of the program and show off what the team accomplished. Feedback for facilitators on their guidance is always welcome as well!

SKILLS

Creativity

Communication

Visual Design Skills

Feedback Skills

SESSION OVERVIEW

Participants gather together to present and answer questions to their peers and facilitators.

KEY TERMS

Feedback

Reactions, thoughts, and opinions of your presentation audience

OBJECTIVE

Present projects to peers and receive feedback.

SESSION EXERCISE

Develop Presentation

As a team, use the pitch template provided to deliver a short 5-minute presentation on your social impact concept project.

Storytelling is a big part of the design process as it's our best tool for convincing other people of the value of our creations.

Consider how to communicate who is involved and who benefits most from the solution. How can you best explain the value of your solution?

Personas

Using personas to connect your solutions to real people and real problems is a powerful way to create empathy in your audience.

Be Concise

There is no need to overload your presentation with information. Keep it simple.

DAY 4 FEEDBACK & REFLECTION

Qualitative feedback and reflective question here..

Qualitative feedback and reflective question here..